

CRYSTALLINE COMPONENTS OF THE BARK OF *PRUNUS PUDDUM*, ROXB. PART III

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The compound, m. p. 150-52°, isolated from *Prunus puddum*, has been shown to contain the flavanone sakuranetin (m. p. 152°) along with traces of another compound (m. p. 198-200°). Diacetyl sakuranetin (m. p. 166-68°) has been described. The acetyl derivative of sakuranetin (m. p. 97°) described by Asahina and co-workers seems to be an impure substance.

A hard, shining, colourless crystalline solid (m. p. 150-52°) has been isolated from the bark of *Prunus puddum* Roxb. (N. O. Rosaceae) (Chakravarti and Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **21**, 173). This compound (C₁₈H₁₄O₆) shows identical colour reactions as the flavanone, sakuranetin (I) (Asahina, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1908, **246**, 259; Asahina, Shinoda and Inubuse, *J. Pharm. Soc.*, Japan, 1927, No. 550, p. 133; 1928, No. 553, p. 29) and some of its derivatives are also similar to the derivatives of sakuranetin, but the methoxyl value is much higher than that required by sakuranetin. Further, it does not form the acetyl derivative (m. p. 97°) described by Asahina and co-workers (*ibid.*, 1927).

TABLE I

	Compound (m. p. 150-52°).	Sakuranetin (m. p. 152°).
Coloration with ferric chloride	Violet	Violet
Coloration with fuming nitric acid	Indigo-blue rapidly changed to violet	Indigo-blue rapidly changed to violet
Coloration with magnesium powder and hydrochloric acid	Pinkish violet which deepens gradually	Pinkish violet which deepens gradually
Tetramethyl ether	Yellow plates, m. p. 119°	Yellow plates, m. p. 119°
Dimethyl ether	Colourless needles, m. p. 116-17°	Colourless needles, m. p. 116°
Triacetyl derivative	Colourless prisms, m. p. 144-46°	Colourless prisms, m. p. 145°
Oxime	Colourless needles, m. p. 198-200°	Colourless needles, m. p. 198-200°

The melting point of the compound does not rise on repeated crystallisations from different solvents. On high vacuum distillation it distils at 195°-205°/0.5 mm. and at

165°/0.2 mm., but the methoxyl content of the distilled product is still much higher than that required for sakuranetin.

The substance has been acetylated under various conditions and the different acetyl derivatives deacetylated with interesting results. With acetic anhydride and concentrated sulphuric acid, a gummy product is obtained, which could not be crystallised. Attempts to prepare the acetyl derivative (m. p. 97°) described by Asahina have been unsuccessful.

When a few drops of pyridine are used as a condensing agent, a small amount of well defined needles, m. p. 145°, is obtained; the melting point is the same as that of triacetyl sakuranetin (2:6:4'-triacetyl-4-methoxychalkone) described by Asahina and his co-workers (*ibid.*, 1928).

When acetylated with acetic anhydride in the presence of freshly fused sodium acetate, three distinct products are isolated.

(i) The acetyl derivative, m. p. 144-46°, evidently triacetyl sakuranetin, which on deacetylation with 15% sulphuric acid gives the original substance, m. p. 150-51°. This deacetylated product has the methoxyl content as required by sakuranetin.

(ii) An acetyl derivative, m. p. 166-68°, which on deacetylation also gives the original substance, m. p. 151°. The analytical data show that it is the diacetyl derivative of sakuranetin. This has not been described by Asahina and the acetyl derivative (m. p. 97°), obtained by him by acetylation in presence of sulphuric acid, appears to be an impure substance. It gives a pink colour with magnesium powder and hydrochloric acid.

(iii) A very small quantity of the acetyl derivative, m. p. 214-16°. On deacetylation, it gives a compound, m. p. 198-200°. It does not give any coloration with ferric chloride, but with magnesium powder and hydrochloric acid it gives a pink colour.

Thus, it is found that the substance, m. p. 150-52°, is not pure sakuranetin but a mixture of two compounds, e.g., (1) sakuranetin, m. p. 152° and (2) unknown compound, m. p. 198-200°.

Mahal, Rai and Venkataraman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 866; 1936, 569) and Chakravarti and Datta (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 639) have observed that certain flavanones or even some chalcones are oxidised by selenium dioxide smoothly to give rise to flavones. It was expected that oxidation of sakuranetin with selenium dioxide would lead to puddumetin (Genkawanin) isolated from the same plant (Chakravarti and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*), but all attempts to oxidise it with selenium dioxide using different solvents have failed.

It is interesting to note that a flavone (Puddumetin, m. p. 278-80°), an isoflavone (Prunasetin, m. p. 237-38°) and a flavanone (sakuranetin, m. p. 150-52°) have been isolated from the same plant, e.g., the bark of *Prunus puddum*.

EXPERIMENTAL

The substance was isolated as described by Chakravarti and Ghosh (*loc. cit.*). It forms shining, hard, almost colourless crystals, m. p. 150-52°. On high vacuum dis-

tillation it distils at 195° - $205^{\circ}/0.5$ mm. and at $165^{\circ}/0.2$ mm. It is readily soluble in cold caustic alkalis but insoluble in cold alkali carbonate and bicarbonate solutions. It gives a violet coloration with ferric chloride solution, indigo-blue coloration which rapidly changes into violet with fuming nitric acid. When reduced with magnesium powder and alcoholic hydrochloric acid in the presence of a drop of mercury, a pinkish violet coloration is produced.

The pure sample was dried over P_2O_5 in vacuum at 100 - 105° for 2 hours and was then analysed. [Found: C, 66.43; H, 4.91; OMe, 12.74. $C_{15}H_{11}O_6(OMe)$ requires C, 67.13; H, 4.89; OMe, 10.84 per cent].

Preparation of Acetyl Derivatives

(i) *Pyridine used as Condensing Agent.*—The substance (0.5 g.) was heated for 2 hours with acetic anhydride and a few drops of dry pyridine. The mixture was diluted with water and warmed on the water-bath for a few minutes. A viscous semi-solid mass separated and this on repeated treatment with ether deposited needles, m. p. 145° , sparingly soluble in ether. [Found: C, 63.87; H, 5.02; OMe, 7.70. $C_{15}H_8O(OCOCH_3)_2$, OMe requires C, 64.08; H, 4.85; OMe, 7.52 per cent].

(ii) *Concentrated Sulphuric Acid as Condensing Agent.*—The substance was heated for an hour with acetic anhydride and 2 to 3 drops of concentrated sulphuric acid. The mixture became dark in colour and was diluted with water and warmed when a turbid solution was obtained. This was extracted with ether, the ethereal extract washed, dried and ether removed when a viscous semi-solid mass separated which could not be crystallised, and on high vacuum distillation (0.2 mm.) it decomposed.

(iii) *Fused Sodium Acetate as Condensing Agent.*—The substance (1 g.) was heated for 6 to 8 hours with acetic anhydride (15 c.c.) and fused sodium acetate (5 g.). The solid obtained after treatment with water was filtered, dried and extracted with methyl alcohol. The residue which remained was crystallised from glacial acetic acid (alternatively from ethyl alcohol) as light brown crystalline powder (0.12 g.), m. p. 214 - 16° . (Found: C, 67.32; H, 4.81; OMe, 6.69 per cent). The methyl alcoholic solution on cooling deposited crystals which were filtered and dissolved in rectified spirit (charcoal) and fractionally crystallised, when two compounds were obtained: (i) colourless, well-defined crystals (0.41 g.), m. p. 144 - 45° and (ii) yellow needles (0.2 g.), m. p. 166 - 68° . [Found in (ii): C, 64.67; H, 4.81; OMe, 8.51. $C_{15}H_9O_2(OCOCH_3)_2$, OMe requires C, 64.86; H, 4.86; OMe, 8.38 per cent].

Deacetylation of Acetyl Compounds and Isolation of Sakuranetin

Triacetyl Compound (m. p. 144 - 45°).—The compound (0.5 g.) and 15% sulphuric acid (20 c.c.) were refluxed for 5 to 6 hours. The solution was cooled and the solid obtained extracted with 10% caustic potash solution, the alkaline solution acidified and the solid obtained was crystallised from benzene and finally from dilute alcohol as colourless needles, m. p. 150 - 51° . [Found: C, 66.88; H, 4.84; OMe, 10.90. $C_{15}H_{11}O_4(OMe)$ requires C, 67.13; H, 4.89; OMe, 10.84 per cent].

This compound gives a deep violet coloration with ferric chloride and pink coloration with magnesium powder and alcoholic hydrochloric acid.

Diacetyl Compound (m. p. 166-68°).—The compound (0.7 g.), and 15% sulphuric acid (20 c.c.) were refluxed for 4 hours over a very small flame and the deacetylated product isolated in the above way, when almost colourless needles, m. p. 151°, were obtained (mixed melting point with the previous sample of sakuranetin). It responded to the colour reactions.

Deacetylation of the Compound (m. p. 214-16°) *and Isolation of a new Compound*.—The substance (0.2 g.) was heated with 15% sulphuric acid (20 c.c.) for 4 hours. The mixture was cooled and the residue after filtration was extracted with 10% caustic potash solution (20 c.c.). Only a part dissolved, the alkaline solution filtered and the filtrate acidified when an orange-red precipitate gradually settled down. The unchanged portion was again heated with 20% sulphuric acid (50 c.c.) and glacial acetic acid (5 c.c.) and worked up in the usual way when an orange-red precipitate was obtained. This was dissolved in rectified spirit, decolorised with animal charcoal, filtered and allowed to crystallise in light brown silky needles, m. p. 198-200° (contraction 197-98°). (Found: C, 70.07; H, 4.82; OMe, 10.01 per cent).

It does not give any coloration with ferric chloride solution but a pink colour is produced with magnesium powder and alcoholic hydrochloric acid.

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